

Medical Pluralism : A Multidimensional Health Behaviour

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Jyotsana Jaiswal

Assistant Professor
Botany
K.P.M. Rajkiya Mahila
Mahavidyalaya
Aurai, Bhadohi, U.P., India

Juhi Singh

Associate Professor
Botany
DDU Government Degree
College
Saidabad, Prayagraj, U.P.,
India

Abstract

The study highlights the growing prevalence of medical pluralism, where individuals blend traditional and conventional medical systems based on their needs, beliefs, and access to care. While biomedicine often holds a dominant role, alternative treatments remain significant, especially among marginalized populations and in rural or developing regions due to affordability, accessibility, and cultural beliefs. In contrast, wealthier individuals often seek traditional or alternative therapies for holistic and personalized care. The use of herbal medicine is especially valued for its perceived effectiveness, affordability, and minimal side effects, particularly in treating chronic or life-threatening conditions. Despite limited awareness of the term medical pluralism, many people practice it unconsciously through their healthcare choices. In the studied region of India, families and tribal communities frequently combine homeopathy, Ayurveda, and allopathic medicine, using a variety of medicinal plants for traditional therapeutic purposes.

Keywords

Medical Pluralism, Herbal Remedies, Ethno-medicine.

Introduction

Human health is one of the basic need which is being considered as dynamic process because it is ever changing due to change in our life style or due to any disease caused by defective nutrition, defective heredity, unfavourable environmental conditions and infections. People need proper medication to keep themselves fit and healthy. It is important to maintain all the constituent of health as it is essential to preserve good life. Though Development of modern medicine is one of the great achievement for human welfare but there is another aspect of these medicines that they are made in labs using synthetic ingredients and often there have side effects to contend with. Some side effects can be quite harsh while some may be milder. These negative side effects are the price to pay thus now a days the study or practice of the medicinal and therapeutic use of plants is being popularize especially as a form of alternative medicine. Herbal supplements of medicine works on a more holistic level or targeting the cause and treating perhaps more mildly but over long term use it has shown to offer good results.

Since ancient times herbal medicine is used by many different cultures throughout the world to treat illness and as supplements, it is also known as herbalism or botanical medicine, Herbal medicine has been used by many different cultures throughout the world for treatment.. Plant extract are complex mixtures of organic compounds which come from different part of a plant. Most of the prescriptive drugs are designed for one specific health problem. There is another aspect of herbal medicine known as ethnomedicine. Ethno medicine is a study or comparison of the traditional medicine practiced by various ethnic groups, and especially by indigenous people.

Medicines, both herbal and pharmaceutical, are big business. But the question of using herbs vs. drugs is not moot. The facts about medicine aside, people often turn to supplements because they're perceived as more natural than drugs, and can have fewer side effects and generally cost less. Due to slow effect and lack of advance researches in the field of herbal medicines people still unable to leave the chemical medicine completely thus a popular concept of medication has been developed in the society known as medical pluralism. It can be defined as the employment of more than one medical system or the use of both conventional and complementary and alternative medicine for health and illness. The word complementary and integrative medicine describe the practice of using non-traditional medical methods in conjugation with traditional method. The integration and coexistence of multiple medical system is significantly relevant in present life style

which provide holistic approach of treatment which include traditional, herbal and modern medicine

The concept of herbal remedies often originated in tribes and ethnic groups from ancient time. Every tribe has a mechanism that has been developed specifically for its culture, and its practitioners use it to preserve knowledge and perform strategic methods to eradicate the majority of the chronic diseases that plague modern society. Additionally, it can serve as a strong basis for the development and expansion of contemporary medicinal medications. The preservation and use of biological heritage depend on the method used to record indigenous knowledge through ethno-botanical studies. People are becoming more aware of herbal medicines and their use because of the negative effects of contemporary allopathic medications. The market for traditional therapies is expanding steadily worldwide, but the number of traditional healers is declining, western lifestyles are having an impact, and knowledge of medicinal plants is rapidly declining. The history of herbalism has been closely linked to the history of medicine since prehistoric times until the advent of the germ theory of disease in the nineteenth century. 19th-century medicine until the present has been based on evidence accumulated by means of the scientific method. Evidence-based usage of pharmaceutical medicines, usually from medicinal plants, has supplanted much of the herbal therapy in contemporary healthcare. The history of herbalism also intersects with food history because much of the herbs and spices used by humans over time to flavor food provide valuable medicinal constituents to protect them from daily food born and other microbial infections. The ancient knowledge system brought with the idea of medical diagnosis treatment and surgery.

With the advancement of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry, medicine was heavily professionalized now a days, the pharmacological treatment of disease began long ago with the use of herbs... it already has. People are often worried about the side effects most medications have and have in turn done a lot of research before swallowing anything. Most medications come in all kinds of colours which can be harmful to the body. Most vitamins and supplements are filled with all kinds of binders and fillers that are synthetic. Using medicinal herbs can sometimes be better than using medical drugs. Some herbs can be mixed with food. When you hear the phrase "herbal remedies," it may conjure up images of dreadlocked hippies offering up flower oil at the local farmer's market and swearing it cures anything from stress to aches to the common cold. When we think of naturopathic medicine, there's a new-age stigma of skepticism that makes it hard for these methods to be taken seriously, even though many herbs have been scientifically proven to have an abundance of positive benefits. There is still much to be gained from herbal remedies, and they often offer several advantages over prescription drugs. One of the biggest benefits of herbal medicine is that the risk of adverse effects which is significantly less than modern medicine. Herbs generally have fewer and less extreme side effects, and they are safer than prescription medications. Herbal remedies are comparatively easy to access than other modern treatment. Herbal drugs can be used to for those also who are sensitive to modern chemical drugs. In some cases herbal drugs are seen to be more potent than advanced chemical combinations. They are natural and can also be used as supplement in daily routine. The natural remedies can be used to prevent all type of diseases even which are considered fatal. Only limitations of these treatments are lack of regulation and dosage instructions but as herbal medicine will become more popular, it is becoming easier to find trained professionals and even naturopathic doctors who can advise on the safest and most effective ways to use herbal medication. Present study deals with review and study of coexistence various popular medicine system.

Objective of study

The study highlights the growing prevalence of medical pluralism, where individuals blend traditional and conventional medical systems based on their needs, beliefs, and access to care.

Review of Literature

A thorough review of existing studies to identify key themes, patterns, and research gaps in the field of medical pluralism have been done. District Mirzapur was selected for the study the research objective. Twenty families in set of five have been selected randomly from different localities of the studied area and grouped into economically sound family, Family with average economy and economically marginalized Family. A questionnaire have been prepared to record their responses, Following questions usually asked to the head of the family as representative as How many medicine system do you know about? Which type of treatment you use first after observing the health problem? How you come to know about home remedies or traditional method? Have you successfully treated the health problems by the treatment other than established treatment method? How frequently you use the traditional and alternative medical system? How does medical pluralism affect health outcomes? Name of the plants and remedies used by those people in the family were asked and recorded. Gathered diverse viewpoints through structured group discussions, revealing shared and contrasting experiences. On the basis of different studies and these questions of study area research objective was observed and

concluded.

Methodology

The present study was done by using different approaches to understand how individuals navigate different healthcare systems and also the factors influencing their choices. Studies involved combined methods to provide a more comprehensive understanding of medical pluralism like survey, interview, analysis of patient records and ethnographic methods of studied area. Extensive studies identify relationships between socio-demographics, health system use, and health outcomes. Systematic Literature Review:

Study Location:

The Indian state of Uttar Pradesh has 75 districts, including Mirzapur. Geographically, it is bordered to the north by the districts of Bhadohi and Varanasi, to the east by Chandauli, to the south by Madhya Pradesh's Sonbhadra and Rewa districts, and to the northwest by Prayagraj district. The district of Mirzapur is about 650 kilometers away from Delhi and Kolkata. It has good access to major cities, being about 67 kilometers from Varanasi and 87 kilometers from Allahabad (Prayagraj). According to the 2011 Census, The area of Mirzapur district is about 4,521 square kilometers in size is home to 2,496,970 people. There were 1,312,302 men and 1,184,668 women in this population.

Result and Discussion

During the studies it has observed that Medical pluralism may not be a term that many people are familiar with, but they frequently grasp the idea from their daily healthcare decisions and experiences. One example of pluralistic healthcare behaviour is the widespread use of both traditional and conventional medical systems to treat various medical conditions. Studies in this field frequently focus more on the frequency of particular medical procedures than on how well-known the term is. However, the idea is

becoming more and more well-known, especially in the medical and academic sectors. Cultural and geographic contexts influence the awareness and practice of medical pluralism, which is a worldwide phenomenon. The concept is gaining increasing recognition worldwide, similarly most of the family in studied area were not aware of the term still they use the traditional methods and home remedies, Most of the families homeopathic and Ayurveda system of medicine along with modern allopathic medicines to get quick and confirm remedy. They use number of plant and plant products, though there are many plants, their parts and plant products are used as medicine for traditional therapeutic uses but some are very common in the study area and used by the common people and tribes. Some medicinal plants and their mode of administration in varies families and tribal community of the region in India is tabulated in following Table.

Table: Uses of Some Medicinal plants

Botanical name	Local/Vernacular name	Disease	Plant Part Used	Mode of administration
Aloe barbadensis	Ghrita Kanwar	Skin Problems	Leaves	1-2 teaspoonful of leaf juice orally and apply on infected part
Aegle marmelos	Bel	Dysentery, Burning sensation	Pulp of fruit	Sharabat of fruit pulp
Artocarpus lakoocha	Lakoocha, Monkey jack	Asthama, colic, Juandice	Fruit	Fresh fruits are use.
Averrhoa carambola	Kamrakh	Jaundice	Fruit and Leaves	Juice of fruit and leaf are use for treatment.
Allium sativum L.	Lehsun	Diarrhoea, earache	Cloves,Leaves	Cloves of garlic as whole, boiled in oil
Aconitum heterophyllum	Atees	Abdominal pain and vomiting	Dry Root	Dry root powder boiled in water. Root is also chewed twice a day.
Achyranthes aspera	Latjeera, Apamarg	Boils, colic, dropsy, ear complications	Whole plant	Dry form of leaves and plant or decoction
Acorus calamus	Bacha, safedbah, Vekanda	Antidote to marijuana, Sinus congestion	Whole Plant	Juice of plant and tuber paste is taken orally.
Baliosperm montanum	Nagadenth	Piles	Root	Root paste is applied over piles.
Chonemorpha fragrans	Perumkurumba	Skin diseases, Purify blood	Root	Paste is applied over skin.
Capparis sepiaziz	Kather	Itching	Leaves	Bath with leaf decoction.

Cucumis colossus	Cogn	Finger infection	Fruit	An infected finger is placed int
Calotropis giganteam	Safed aak, madar	Vomiting therapy, abdominal tumors, bloating	Leaves, stem bark, latex	Latex, Decoction of the plant
Cassia sophera	Kalkasunda	Skin disease	leaves	Leaf juice is applied inn ringworm
Crotalaria albida	Banatasi	Body swelling	Root	Root decoction mixed with 2-3 spoon ginger extract is taken regularly in empty stomach
Cuscuta reflexa	Dodder, Giant dodder	Jaundice, cough, Urinary infection	Whole plant	Plant juice mixed with coconut water
Dillenia pentagyna	Agatchi	Diabetics stomachache, piles, Bone Fracture	Bark, leaf	Powder of Bark is used.
Euphorbia hirta.	Duddhi, Bara dudhhi	Bronchitis, Asthama, Juandice, Gonorrhoea, Worm infection in children	Leaves	Leaf paste or plant Paste or decoction
Haldinia cordifolia	Kadam, Haldu	Intestinal worms, liver infection	Stem bark	Decoction of Bark
Moringa pterygosperma	Munga, Sehjan	Cold and cough, Joint Pain, Diabetes	Leaves, Flower, Gum	Leaf powder with mustard oil is given orally for 3 days.
Tectona grandis	Sagwan	Skin infection	Wood	Wood oil
Vinca rosea	Sadabahar	Diabetes	Leaves and Flowers	Crushed leaves decoction
Vitex negundo	Chines chaste	Ear pain, Rheumatism, Abortion	Leaves	Leaves powder with cow milk

Conclusion

The study reveals that medical pluralism, where individuals actively mix or blend different treatment system is increasingly prevalent in the modern world. This practice reflects a dynamic approach to healthcare, where users engage with multiple medical traditions based on need, belief, and accessibility. Within this framework, biomedicine (or allopathic medicine) often holds a dominant position over alternative medical systems. However, the integration of various treatment modalities underscores the importance of recognizing diverse medical perspectives and patient experiences.

Several factors contribute to the use of alternative medicine, including cultural norms, social contexts, and economic conditions. The choice to combine different medical systems is influenced not only by the availability of treatments but also by patients' personal understanding of health and healing. Notably, medical pluralism is especially prevalent among marginalized and underserved populations than others.

In rural areas, developing countries, and regions with limited access to modern healthcare infrastructure, traditional methods of treatment are often preferred. This preference is driven by affordability, accessibility, deep-rooted cultural beliefs, and the perception that traditional remedies carry fewer side effects compared to biomedical interventions.

On the other hand, economically affluent populations may turn to traditional or alternative medicine for different reasons. These can include the pursuit of complementary therapies, holistic or preventative care, and a desire for more personalized treatment options. For these groups, traditional practices often appeal due to their perceived ability to address health in a more integrated and individualized manner. In the modern world it has been realized the herbal drugs strengthens the body system specifically and selectively without side effects. The importance of traditional herbal medicinal system has now gained vital importance in developed and developing countries is worthy. It is cost effective more affordable system of medication with fewer side effect. The use of herbal medicine for chronic diseases such as advance stages of cancer when

conventional medicine become ineffective is a new face of herbal medicine and promotion of these medication in life threatening conditions is in human welfare.

Author Contributions

The authors contributed equally to the conceptualization, methodology, data analysis, and manuscript writing.

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References

1. Adams V. *Establishing proof: translating Science and the state in Tibetan medicine*. In *New horizons in medical anthropology: essays in honour of Charles Leslie* (eds) M. Nichter & M. Lock, New York: Routledge, 200-20.
2. Armstrong, David. *Political Anatomy of the Body: Medical Knowledge in Britain in the Twentieth Century*. Cambridge University Press, 1983.
3. Banerjee Madhulika. —Whither Indigenous Medicinell Seminar, 2000; 45: 489.
4. Bhardwaj SM. *Medical pluralism and homeopathy: a geographic perspective*. *Soc Sci Med Med Anthropol*, 1980; 14B(4): 209-16.
5. Billing Jennifer, Sherman PW. "Antimicrobial functions of spices: why some like it hot". *Q Rev Biol*. 1998; 73(1):3-49. doi:10.1086/420058. PMID 9586227.
6. Cant S. *Medical Pluralism, Mainstream Marginality or Subaltern Therapeutics? Globalization and the Integration of 'Asian' Medicines and Biomedicine in the UK. Society and Culture in South Asia.*, 2020; 6(1): 31–51.
7. Chandra S. *Status of Indian medicine and folk healing: With a focus on the integration of AYUSH medical systems in healthcare delivery*. *Ayu.*, Oct, 2012; 33(4): 461-65.
8. Chengpu Yu. *Medical Pluralism in a Dong village, southwestern China*. *International Journal of Anthropology and Ethnology*, 2021; 5(2).
9. *Complementary and Alternative Medicine Products and their Regulation by the Food and Drug Administration, 2007; cited on 25/11/ 2022. Available from: <https://www.fda.gov/>.*
10. Crandon-Malamud L. *From the fat of our souls: social change, political process, and medical pluralism in Bolivia*. University of California Press, 1991.
11. *Diseases*. *Clin Dermatol*, 2008; 26(1): 62-78.
12. Dube A, Bartlett G, Morales J, Evans A, Doucet A, Caudarella A, et al. *The Chilcapamba-McGill Partnership: Exploring Access to Maternal and Newborn Care in Indigenous Communities of Ecuador*. *Prog Community Health Partnerships. Research education and action*, 2015; 9(3): 327-34.
13. Field T. *Yoga research review*. *Complement Ther Clin Pract.*, 2016; 24: 145-61.
14. Hampshire, K. & S. Owusu. *Grandfathers, Google, and dreams: medical pluralism, globalization, and new healing encounters in Ghana*. *Medical Anthropology*, 2012; 32: 247-65.
15. Lai PK, Roy J. "Antimicrobial and chemopreventive properties of herbs and spices". *Curr. Med. Chem.* 2004; 11(11):1451-60. doi:10.2174/0929867043365107. PMID 15180577.
16. Leslie, *Medical pluralism in world perspective*. *Social Science and Medicine*, 1980; 14: 191-95. Lai PK, Roy J. "Antimicrobial and chemopreventive properties of herbs and spices". *Curr. Med. Chem.* 2004; 11(11):1451-60. doi:10.2174/0929867043365107. PMID 15180577.
17. *Ministry of Health and Family Welfare (MoHFW) Government of India. National Health Policy 1983, Cited on 25/11/22. Available at <https://.nhp.gov.in/>*
18. *Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. Report of the working group on AYUSH for the 12th five-year plan (2012e17).cited on 25/11/2022. Available at <http://planningcommission.nic.in/aboutus/committee>*
19. *National Rural Health Mission. Government of India 2005-12. Mission document, MoHFW 2005, New Delhi. Cited on 25/11/2022 Available at <http://main.mohfw.gov.in/document/policy>.*
20. *Rashtriya Bal Swasthya Karyakram, National Health Mission, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. Cited on 25/11/2022 Available from, <http://nrhm.gov.in/nrhm-components/mnch-a/child-health-immunization/rashtriya-bal-swasthya-karyakram-rbsk/background.html>.*
21. Reddy S., Qadeer I. *Medical tourism in India: progress or predicament? Economic and Political Weekly*, 2010; 45: 69-75.
22. Ruhil R. *Medical Pluralism in India and Its Integration into State Health Service System*. *Ayushdhara*, 2015; 2(5): 309-14.
23. Sheehan, H.E, *Medical pluralism in India: patient choice or no other options? Indian J Med Ethics*, 2009; 6(3): 138-41.
24. Shih CC, Su YL, Liao CC, and Lin JG. *Patterns of Medical Pluralism among adults: results from the 2001 National Health Interview Survey in Taiwan*. *BMC Health*

- Services Research*, 2010; 10: 191.
25. Sujatha V and Abraham L. *‘Medicine, State and Society’ Economic and Political. weekly research foundation*, 2009; 44(16): 83.
 26. Sundararaman T. *National Health Policy 2017: a cautious welcome. Indian J Med Ethics*, 2017; 2(2): 69-71.
 27. Susan Sam. "Importance and effectiveness of herbal medicines." *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*. 2019; 8(2): 354-357 E-ISSN: 2278-4136 P-ISSN: 2349-8234 JPP 2019; 8(2): 354-357.
 28. Susan Sam. "Importance and effectiveness of herbal medicines." *Journal of Pharmacognosy and Phytochemistry*. 2019; 8(2): 354-357 E-ISSN: 2278-4136 P-ISSN: 2349-8234 JPP 2019; 8(2): 354-357
 29. Tapsell LC, Hemphill I, Cobiac L et al. "Health benefits of herbs and spices: the past, the present, the future". *Med. J. Aust.* 2006; 185(4):S4-24. PMID 17022438.
 30. Tapsell LC, Hemphill I, Cobiac L et al. "Health benefits of herbs and spices: the past, the present, the future". *Med. J. Aust.* 2006; 185(4):S4-24. PMID 17022438.
 31. Thas JJ. *Siddha medicine--background and principles and the application for skin*
 32. Thomson P, Jones J, Evans JM, Leslie SL. *Factors influencing the use of complementary and alternative medicine and whether patients inform their primary care physician. Complement Ther Med.* 2012;20:45–53.
 33. Torri, M. C. *Choosing between traditional medicine and allopathy during pregnancy: Health practices in prenatal and reproductive health care in Ecuador. Journal of Health Management*, 2013; 15(3): 397.
 34. Singh Usha and Satyanarain *Ethanobotanical wealth of Mirzapur district (U.P.) Indian Forester* 2009; 136(2): 187-195.
 35. *World Health Organization: Geneva. WHO Traditional Medicine Strategy 2014–2023, cited on 16/11/22 Available at <http://www.who.int/>.*